

RARE DISEASES IN THE SADC REGION

Background

Rare diseases, also referred to as orphan diseases, are disorders that affect a small proportion of a population.

10,000+

Rare Diseases

80%

of Rare diseases
are of Genetic origin

300M+

Live with Rare
Diseases

Problem Statement

Being rare, there is a deficit of medical and scientific knowledge on the diseases. This impacts diagnosis, treatment and management of the diseases causing difficulties in accessing healthcare for people living with rare diseases (PLRD). Public health policy is also still catching up with provision of healthcare and social services to people living with rare diseases.

Analysis – SADC Region

In Sub-Saharan Africa and particularly the SADC region there is a deficit of information on rare diseases including the type of diseases and number of affected individuals.

Recommendations

A unified policy framework for diagnostic, treatment and research on rare diseases in the SADC region.

- Capacity building for healthcare workers
- Create a centralised registry of rare diseases demographics
- Establishment of rare diseases centres and units under ministries of health
- Foster research in rare diseases as well as discovery and development of orphan drugs
- Cost bearing and universal health insurance coverage
- Ensuring provision of social services such as counselling and psychological support, and homeschooling.

The Coalition

